

INCORPORATION OF OXIDE FIBRES IN GLASS MATRIX COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY: The introduction of Nextel 440[®] fibres for reinforcement tasks in glass matrix composites has been studied. The ceramic fibres were coated with thin layers (< 100 nm) of pyrolytic carbon to prevent diffusion between fibre and glassy matrix. The carbon coating has been produced by CVD technique or by liquid phase coating and additional pyrolysis. At first uncoated fibre material was investigated after different heat treatments by XRD-analysis. Tensile tests with coated and uncoated fibres after heat treatments have been carried out. The ceramic fibres, protected by liquid phase coating, show lower tensile strength than coated by CVD-technology.

Carbon coated fibre reinforced glass composites were fabricated by slurry infiltration and hot-pressing. Significant increase in bending strength and work of fracture have been noticed for fibre reinforced glass matrix composites. These effects are related to the low bonding between fibre and matrix, caused by a fibre coating.

KEYWORDS: ceramic fibres, crystallization behaviour, XRD-analysis, tensile strength, glass matrix, fibre coating, liquid phase coating, pyrolytic carbon.

INTRODUCTION

The brittle nature, and therefore, high susceptibility to catastrophic failure of glass and ceramic materials limits their use in applications. By reinforcing a low modulus, low strength glass matrix with high modulus, high strength fibres, it is possible to obtain glass composites with improved properties. In general the resulting properties of the composite vary strongly depending on the characteristics and the geometry of the reinforcing elements used and on the properties of the interface between matrix and fibre. A glass matrix is widely used in combination with carbon and silicon carbide fibres to form composites. This paper deals with Nextel 440[®] ceramic fibres for applications in glass matrix composites.

The best results in terms of increasing the fracture tolerance and creating a pseudo-ductile fracture behaviour to brittle matrices is achieved with continuous fibre reinforcement. [1]. The majority of work concerned with fibre reinforcement of glasses and glass-ceramics has focused on using SiC- or carbon fibres. The reinforcement of glass matrices by continuous

alumina or mullite filaments has been much less investigated [2, 3, 4] than with carbon or SiC-fibres.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES AND RESULTS

Materials

Commercially available Nextel 440[®] fibres with an equivalent fibre diameter of 11.4 μm were used. The glass matrix employed was a borosilicate glass (8330, SCHOTT GLASS, Mainz, Germany). Chemical composition and characteristic properties of fibres and matrix are given in table 1. The glass was milled and sieved. All particles of the glass powder were $< 40 \mu\text{m}$.

Table 1: *Characteristic properties (manufacturer data)*

Glass	Bending strength [MPa]	Young`s modulus [GPa]	Thermal expansion coeff. [10^{-6}K^{-1}] ∞ (20-300)	Density [g/cm^3]
8330	90	63	3.3	2.23
Fibre	Tensile strength [MPa]	Young`s modulus [GPa]	Thermal expansion coeff. [10^{-6}K^{-1}] ∞ (25-500)	Density [g/cm^3]
Nextel 440 [®]	2070	186	4.38	3.05

Fibre coating

The fibres were coated by continuous CVD-technique at 900 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ in argon atmosphere (TU Chemnitz-Zwickau, Lehrstuhl Physikalische Chemie) or with a Novolak layer. The weight content of Novolak in the ethanol solution was varied. The thickness of the carbon layers was calculated from results of thermogravimetry using density of carbon and fibres, filament count and diameter. After heat cleaning (removing of sizing at 500 $^{\circ}\text{C}$) the yarn was pulled through the Novolak solution, dried and collected on a ceramic coil. Later the Novolak layer was pyrolyzed to carbon at 1000 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ in vacuum atmosphere. The thickness of the carbon layer of CVD-coated fibres is 45 nm. We calculated a thickness of 70 nm for carbon layers produced with 2.5 wt-% Novolak solution.

Tensile testing

Before the preparation of composites the fibre material itself was analyzed regarding its behaviour after heat treatment and with different coatings.

Single filament strength testing was performed using rubber-faced clamp grips with $12 \times 25 \text{ mm}^2$ grip faces. The fibres were glued on paper frames like recommended in DIN ENV 1007-4 [5]. The machine compliance was determined from different gauge length according [5]. Young`s modulus was calculated using machine compliance. The tested gauge length were 26, 52, 104 and 156 mm. The strain rate was 0.01 min^{-1} . During fibre testing, no fibre remained in the gauge length after fracture. Fibre diameter was measured on fibre ends

removed from the grips after fibre failure. If this was not possible, a mean diameter determined on 200 fibres of the same material was used for calculations. The fibre diameters were measured using a high resolution optical microscope Axiotech (1000× magnification) Carl Zeiss with image analysis software KS 3000.

Fig. 1 shows tensile strength of Nextel 440[®] fibres as a function of temperature of heat treatment. The filaments were heated up for 5 h for the given temperature. Tensile strength was measured at room temperature (gauge length 26 mm).

Fig. 1: Tensile strength of Nextel 440[®] fibres after 5 h heat treatment at elevated temperatures.

The determined Young's modulus of the fibre material is 150 GPa up to 1100 °C heat treatment. At 1200 °C and higher temperatures the Young's modulus increased to 200 GPa.

Fig. 2 shows the XRD-pattern of the crystalline phase of Nextel 440[®] fibres after heat treatment at elevated temperatures. The peak at 26.2° in the XRD-pattern for 500°C heat treating indicates quartz crystallization during heat cleaning. Up to 1100 °C the microstructure of the fibre seems to be almost unchanged compared to the as-received fibre.

After a heat treatment at temperatures of 1200 °C and higher mullite crystallized. The double peak at 26 ° indicates an orthorhombic crystal structure of the mullite.

The grain size of the mullite phase changes between 290 nm after heat treatments at 1200°C and 370 nm at 1500°C. These values were calculated from the XRD-analysis. SEM investigations confirm this level of grain sizes.

Fig. 2: XRD-pattern of Nextel 440® fibres after 5 h heat treatment at elevated temperatures.

Fig. 3 shows the tensile strength of Nextel 440® fibres as a function of gauge length. This figure contains as received fibres, fibres after heat treatment, fibres after CVD coating and fibres coated by liquid phase and additional pyrolysis. At minimum 25 filaments were measured for each data point.

As received Nextel 440® fibres show a tensile strength of 1931 MPa (26 mm gauge length) after heat cleaning. This is a slightly lower value than published in the product information of the manufacturer (2070 MPa) [6].

Fig. 3: Tensile strength of four lots of Nextel 440® single fibres as a function of gauge length with different coatings and heat treatments. The line is the least squares fit of the mean strength of the data points of every lot.

CVD-coated Nextel 440® fibres have the highest tensile strength of all tested fibres. For CVD coated fibres mean tensile strength decreased from 1900 to 1789 MPa (decrease by 6 %) for a

6-fold increase in gauge length. The reduction of tensile strength with increasing gauge length was small for as received and CVD coated fibres.

Nextel 440[®] fibres coated with Novolak solution (2.5 wt-%) with additional pyrolysis at 1000 °C of the Novolak show no dependence of tensile strength on gauge length but a lower level of tensile strength (1560 MPa). This is a decrease of tensile strength by 20 %. The low increase of tensile strength with increasing gauge length is within the standard deviation of the mean strength over the gauge length.

Heat treated fibres show a strong dependence of tensile strength on gauge length. There is a decrease of tensile strength by 32 % for a 6-fold increase in gauge length.

Helmer et. al. [7] published results of the effect of the thickness of pyrolytic carbon layers on the strength of T800H carbon fibres. These fibres were coated by CVD-technology. They found that thickness up to 17 nm does not effect the fibre strength. Larger thickness of the carbon layer lead to a decrease of fibre strength. A fibre coating of 50 nm thickness decreased fibre strength to 58 %. As a result of these investigations it was our aim to coat the fibres with thin carbon layers.

Hot pressing and sample testing

Ceramic fibre tows were impregnated with < 40µm glass powder using conventional slurry winding techniques. As binder a 0.5 wt-% polyvinylalcohol solution was used. Unidirectional composite samples were manufactured by hot pressing in vacuum atmosphere at 850°C. Pressure was 5 MPa, dwell time 45 min. Pressure was applied when maximum temperature was achieved. The composite plates were cut into sample bars of 6 × 1.5 × 40 mm³ size. The sample bars were tested in 3-point-bending tests carried out at room temperature with an universal testing equipment (Instron 4467) at a crosshead speed of 1 mm/min. Span was 30 mm.

Nextel 440[®] reinforced glass matrix composites (uncoated fibres) show a slightly higher bending strength compared to the unreinforced matrix glass. They have a catastrophic failure behaviour like the unreinforced glass matrix. No pull out effect is observed in this system. This behaviour is related to the strong bonding between fibre and matrix.

The bending strength of CVD coated Nextel 440[®]/ borosilicate glass matrix composites reaches 349 MPa at a fibre volume of 32 %. Fig. 5 gives the stress-strain behaviour of these composites.

The work of fracture of the composite with CVD coated fibres is 3250 N/m (calculated for 50% maximum load) compared to 3 N/m for unreinforced glass. The work of fracture of the composite with liquid phase coated fibres is 400 N/m. The carbon coating applied to the fibres influences the fracture toughness as indicated by the stress/strain curve. This toughness increases due to the delamination phenomena. The tensile stress in the marginal fibre layers becomes larger than the fracture strength in this area. The cracks through the samples are deflected along the fibre/matrix interface. Fig. 6 shows a laser scanning micrograph (Leica TCS E) of a composite with carbon coated fibres (liquid phase coating with additional pyrolysis). The arrow marks a crack, deflected on a weak fibre/matrix interface.

Fig. 5: Stress/strain behaviour of glass matrix composites with different coated fibres.

Fig. 6: Laser Scanning micrograph of a carbon coated fibre composite.

Conclusions

Carbon coatings on Nextel 440[®] fibres have been investigated. Single CVD coated Nextel 440[®] fibres show no decrease in tensile strength compared to uncoated fibres. Pyrolytic carbon produced by liquid phase coating degrades the single fibre strength.

The application of uncoated oxide fibres in glass matrix composites results in a strong, diffusion bonded fibre/matrix interface. The application of carbon coatings to the fibres prevents diffusion bonding between the matrix and the fibre and a debonded interface is developed. Composites fabricated from carbon coated fibres show improved bending strength and work of fracture. Sample investigations with laser scanning microscopy show crack deflection of carbon coated fibres.

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